

The Role of Selenocysteine in Catalysis and Oxygen Tolerance of a W-Dependent Formate Dehydrogenase

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ABSTRACT: Metal-dependent formate dehydrogenases (FDHs) catalyze, under mild conditions, the reversible reduction of CO₂ to formate, a versatile C1 feedstock that can contribute to a carbon-neutral economy. Metal-dependent FDHs are the most widespread selenoproteins found in bacteria, and around 44% of them include selenocysteine (Sec) as a ligand to the Mo/W active site. In the sulfate-reducer *Nitratidulfovibrio vulgaris* Hildenborough, the main FDH responsible for CO₂ reduction is the W/Sec-dependent FdhAB, which is among the most active CO₂ reductases reported so far. In contrast to most metal-dependent FDHs, this enzyme is relatively O₂-tolerant and can be purified aerobically. In this work, we evaluated the role of Sec in the catalytic and stability properties of the W/Sec-FdhAB. For that, a Sec-to-Cys variant (U192C) was created, its catalytic and spectroscopic properties were characterized, and its crystal structure was determined. Sec substitution by Cys strongly affects activity, decreases the *K_M* for formate, and increases susceptibility to O₂. While Sec-to-Cys replacement induces only weak changes of the W^V EPR signals, using ⁷⁷Se-labeled enzyme, we could show that Sec undoubtedly coordinates the W metal in the W^V redox state. The crystal structure of U192C confirmed previous findings on the redox switch mechanism of activation and protection of FdhAB, while revealing a putative catalytic intermediate of FdhAB with Arg441 orienting a CO₂ substrate analog (probably SO₂) in the active site. Overall, the results indicate that Sec plays a critical role in the high activity displayed by W/Sec-FdhAB, and that it may also be involved in or modulate the proton transfer to and from the active site.

KEYWORDS: selenoproteins, CO₂ reduction, tungsten coordination, W^V EPR, protein film electrochemistry

INTRODUCTION

Selenocysteine (Sec), the 21st amino acid in the genetic code, is present in many proteins from high eukaryotes to archaea, but absent in most yeast, fungi, and higher plants.¹ In humans, the 25 selenoproteins present are mostly involved in antioxidant defense and redox regulation of cell metabolism.² However, the role of selenium in human physiology was recently expanded by a study showing that selenide can be used directly to prevent lipid peroxidation and ferroptosis in mitochondria, through its oxidation by sulfide:quinone oxidoreductase, with production of the peroxy radical-trapping ubiquinol.³ In bacteria and archaea, selenoproteins are usually associated with energy metabolism functions, with Sec being almost exclusively found in the catalytic site of enzymes involved in redox catalysis.^{1,4,5} The advantages of selenoproteins over cysteine homologs are usually reflected in higher catalytic rates, although the difference may not be very high, and resistance to irreversible oxidation.^{6–8} The Sec-to-Cys substitution usually leads to a strong decrease in enzymatic activity,^{1,8,9} but exceptions have been reported.^{10,11} While both Se and S belong to the chalcogen group of the periodic table and share many properties, namely similar size, electronegativity, and oxidation states, Se is more polarizable and

has been shown to be a better nucleophile and leaving group in thiol–disulfide exchange reactions.^{1,4,9} Sec also has a lower p*K_a* being mainly ionized at physiological pH, and the redox potential of diselenides (−388 mV) is lower than that of disulfides (−238 mV).^{1,4,9} However, Sec insertion comes at a high cost due to the need for a dedicated and complex biosynthetic machinery,^{12,13} and the process is much more energetically demanding than the incorporation of Cys.⁹

Nevertheless, the influence of the chemical properties of Sec/Cys in an enzymatic reaction is also constrained by the protein matrix, namely, by the local environmental effects involving the polypeptide chain. Cys-containing enzymes can present activities close to Sec-containing ones,⁴ which raises the question of why Nature opts to keep selenoproteins. One of the reasons is linked to the higher electrophilic character of Se-oxides, which are more readily reduced than S-oxides,

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Table 1. Kinetic Characterization of wt-FdhAB and the U192C Variant (Anaerobically Purified)

	Formate			D-Formate			CO ₂			Ref
	k_{cat} (s ⁻¹)	K_{M} (μM)	$k_{\text{cat}}/K_{\text{M}}$ (s ⁻¹ mM ⁻¹)	k_{cat} (s ⁻¹)	K_{M} (μM)	$k_{\text{cat}}/K_{\text{M}}$ (s ⁻¹ mM ⁻¹)	k_{cat} (s ⁻¹)	K_{M} (μM)	$k_{\text{cat}}/K_{\text{M}}$ (s ⁻¹ mM ⁻¹)	
FdhAB	1310 ± 50	17 ± 3	77,060	1070 ± 80	18 ± 2	59,440	315 ± 30	420 ± 45	750	²³ , this work
U192C	56 ± 6	355 ± 45	158	21 ± 2	455 ± 50	46	30 ± 3	210 ± 10	140	this work

preventing irreversible oxidative inactivation, despite Se being more easily oxidized.^{6–8} This reversibility of Se reactions appears to be a critical property for its biological function, as shown recently for glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4), where Sec was shown to play an essential role in the prevention of peroxide-induced ferroptosis due to its resistance to over-oxidation, in contrast to the Cys homologue.¹⁴ Remarkably, in *Escherichia coli* [NiFe] hydrogenase-1, substitution of the three Ni-binding Cys for Sec at the active site differentially affected the activity and response to O₂.¹⁰ In contrast to the Sec-to-Cys replacements, all three Cys-to-Sec substitutions led to a decrease in catalytic efficiency. However, substitution of the Cys corresponding to a Sec in Sec-dependent hydrogenases revealed a dramatic increase in oxygen tolerance, while substitution of the two other Cys that only have a role as Ni ligands actually increased O₂ sensitivity.¹⁰ In the [NiFeSe] hydrogenase from *Nitratidesulfovibrio vulgaris* Hildenborough (*N. vulgaris* H, previously *Desulfovibrio vulgaris* Hildenborough), replacing the native Sec with a Cys led to a strong decrease in activity and an increase in O₂ sensitivity, in line with a special role for this Ni-ligand position.¹⁵ However, the specific role played by Sec is still not clear for many selenoproteins.^{1,5}

The first evidence of Se requirement in bacteria described that Se is mandatory for formate dehydrogenase (FDH) activity in *E. coli*, but only much later was it shown that Se is actually incorporated in this protein.¹⁶ Since then, it has become clear that metal-dependent FDHs are the most widely distributed selenoproteins in bacteria.^{5,17} These enzymes are very interesting for biotechnological exploitation due to their high CO₂ reduction activity.^{18,19} Enzymatic reduction of CO₂ has major advantages over chemical catalysis, due to its absolute product selectivity and the ability to reduce CO₂ close to the CO₂/formate thermodynamic potential,²⁰ at mild temperatures and pressures, without the need for precious metals.²¹ CO₂ reduction occurs at the Mo/W active site, where the metal is coordinated by the dithiolene moieties of two molybdopterin guanine dinucleotides (MGD), and one sulfido group, besides the Sec or Cys protein ligand. Sec is believed to have been the ligand of the Mo/W-bisMGD metal active site in ancestral enzymes,²² and that its substitution by a cysteine residue occurred for several FDHs during evolution.¹⁷ The presence of Sec in ancestral FDHs is aligned with their probable physiological role in CO₂ reduction. Indeed, the most active FDHs in CO₂ reduction are those containing W and/or Sec at the active site.^{23–26} The lower redox potential of W versus Mo^{27,28} makes this metal more suited for the CO₂ reduction reaction, leading to higher enzymatic activities.

In the case of FDHs, the role of the Sec/Cys ligand in the catalytic mechanism is still not fully clear, but the superiority of Sec was demonstrated for the *E. coli* Sec/Mo FDH-H (EcFDH-H), where its substitution by a Cys led to a strong decrease in activity,^{25,29} as observed for other selenoenzymes.^{9,15,30} However, the effect of this substitution on a W-

dependent enzyme has not been studied. The exact role of Sec in the FDH catalytic cycle has long been discussed and remains non-consensual.^{19,31–33} Since this amino acid is not strictly essential in FDHs, understanding its role and the specific features that support the evolutionary pressure to retain it is of great importance, especially in the context of CO₂ reduction. Here, the effect of the Se-for-S substitution on the properties of a W-FDH is studied using one of the most active FDHs in CO₂ reduction, W/Sec-FdhAB from *N. vulgaris*H. Due to its robustness, simple composition, and high CO₂ reduction activity, the W/Sec-FdhAB is an ideal model system for biocatalytic applications.^{21,34} A Sec-to-Cys variant (U192C) of this enzyme was produced, and its catalytic and spectroscopic properties were characterized and integrated with the structural information. The full sulfur coordination of W in the U192C variant strongly affects activity, decreases the K_{M} for formate, and increases susceptibility to O₂. In addition, the characterization of a ⁷⁷Se-labeled FdhAB variant confirms that Sec coordinates the W^V intermediate. Finally, the structural characterization of the U192C variant provided further validation of the previously proposed redox switch mechanism, where a surface allosteric disulfide bond is involved in O₂ protection by controlling the conformation and activity of the enzyme,³⁵ and enabled the identification of a catalytic intermediate analog (binding SO₂) in the CO₂ reduction reaction, which agrees with predictions by computational methods.³⁶

RESULTS

U192C Purification and Kinetic Characterization. The U192C variant was purified under both anaerobic and aerobic conditions. The anaerobically purified U192C enzyme retains only 4.3% (56 ± 6 s⁻¹) and 9.5% (30 ± 3 s⁻¹) of the formate oxidation and CO₂ reduction activity, respectively, compared to the wild-type (WT) Sec-containing enzyme (Table 1). The aerobically purified enzyme displays even less activity in both formate oxidation (25 ± 3 s⁻¹, 1.9% of WT) and CO₂ reduction (14 ± 1 s⁻¹, 4.4% of WT). This indicates an increased O₂-susceptibility induced by the substitution of Se. For subsequent studies, U192C was always purified anaerobically to avoid O₂ damage, therefore not requiring reductive activation with DTT.³⁵ The U192C K_{M} for formate (355 ± 45 μM) is significantly higher than that of the WT-FdhAB, leading to an almost 500-fold lower catalytic efficiency for formate oxidation (Table 1). The U192C K_{M} for CO₂ (210 ± 10 μM) is lower than that of WT-FdhAB (420 ± 45 μM), resulting in a catalytic efficiency for CO₂ reduction 5 times lower than that of the WT.

The activity of WT-FdhAB and the U192C variant was also tested with deuterated formate (D-formate). As expected, D-formate does not lead to a significant difference in K_{M} ($p > 0.61$). However, a kinetic isotope effect was observed, which is stronger for the U192C variant ($k_{\text{cat}}(\text{H})/k_{\text{cat}}(\text{D})=2.7$) than for the WT-FdhAB ($k_{\text{cat}}(\text{H})/k_{\text{cat}}(\text{D})=1.2$) (Table 1 and Figure S1).

Figure 1. pH dependency on U192C activity. pH profile of (A) formate oxidation activity and (B) CO₂ reduction activity. Activities are relative to the maximum activity (100%) observed in each case. All assays were performed in triplicate and error bars represent the standard deviation. WT – light gray, U192C – dark gray.

Figure 2. Effect of O₂ exposure on U192C. (A) Relative formate oxidation activity of samples incubated aerobically: U192C without formate (open orange circles) and with 20 mM formate (full orange circles). Data for the DTT-activated WT-FdhAB without formate (open black squares), and with 20 mM formate (full black squares) is also shown (data from ref 35) (B) Inactivation by O₂ during formate oxidation catalysis, followed by chronoamperometry: Activated WT-FdhAB (black line), U192C (orange line), and fit of eq [1] (gray dotted lines). Experimental conditions: [O₂] = 30 μM $t \approx 60$ s, 1 mM formate, $E = 0.130$ V, pH 7, electrode rotation rate = 4000 rpm. The current was normalized to the value measured before the addition of O₂. (C) Kinetic properties of inactivation by the enzyme by O₂. The data are presented as means ± standard deviation for 3 different experiments, * $p < 0.05$.

The optimal pH for formate oxidation is also affected by the Se substitution: the Cys variant shows a narrower bell-shaped profile, shifted to a lower pH (6 vs 7.6), where the activity is sustained above 80% only between pH 5.5 and 7 (Figure 1A). This effect may be due to changes in the protonation state of active site residues. For CO₂ reduction, the effect is smaller, but the optimal pH is also slightly shifted to a lower pH value, with a broader activity plateau (close to 90%) being maintained between pH 5.3 and 7.5 for U192C (Figure 1B).

O₂ Tolerance. Although aerobic purification of the U192C variant has a strong negative effect on its activity, short-term exposure to air of an anaerobically purified sample does not disturb enzyme activity as long as the enzyme is not in the presence of substrates (Figure 2A), as previously reported for the WT-FdhAB.^{23,35,37} When O₂ exposure occurs in the presence of formate, inactivation is rapidly observed, and U192C loses its activity in less than 30 min, whereas the activated WT-FdhAB still retains some activity under the same conditions, which is congruent with the variant being more O₂-

susceptible than FdhAB (Figure 2A). We used chronoamperometry to follow the direct effect of O₂ during turnover for U192C and WT-FdhAB. As reported previously, the enzyme was coadsorbed with polymyxin, which promotes stable protein-electrode interaction, onto a pyrolytic graphite electrode (PGE-RDE).³⁵ A positive potential ($E = 0.130$ mV) was applied in the presence of formate to measure the current resulting from formate oxidation, which is directly proportional to the instant turnover frequency. Injection of O₂ into the electrochemical cell causes an instant decrease in current, which is more pronounced for U192C than for WT-FdhAB (Figure 2B), followed by a decay that is faster with the variant than with the WT. This behavior can be explained by a 2-step mechanism of enzyme inactivation as described in Equation 1.

The kinetic model assumes that the initial drop in the current is the result of a fast equilibrium between the enzyme and O₂, which produces an inactive O₂-bound state (EO₂). The extent of this initial current drop depends on the O₂ dissociation constant K_{O_2} , a measure of the enzyme's affinity for O₂. The O₂-bound state of the enzyme is converted to the irreversibly inactivated state (E^{inact}) with a first-order rate constant, k_i . Our analysis reveals that the apparent bimolecular rate constant of inactivation by O₂ ($\left(\frac{k_i}{K_{O_2}}\right)$) is around 8 times faster for U192C than for WT-FdhAB, because of a greatly increased affinity for O₂ (≈ 20 times) for the Cys-containing enzyme relative to the WT, combined with a slight decrease in the rate of the second step relative to the WT. The latter observation is consistent with the expectation that Se reacts more quickly with O₂ than sulfur.^{4,7,9}

EPR and ⁷⁷Se Labeling. Previous analysis of WT-FdhAB revealed the presence of two W^V signals,³⁸ whose relative proportion varies depending on the reductant used—formate (F), the enzyme substrate, or dithionite (D),³⁸ which has a lower redox potential and allows enzyme reduction independently of its activity. The two signals, named W^V_F ($g = 1.995, 1.881, 1.852$) and W^V_D ($g = 1.993, 1.909, 1.852$), respectively, differ mainly in the g_2 -value, which was interpreted from DFT calculations as a result of small variations in the SSSS dihedral angles of the bis-MGD planes,³⁸ while Sec is always coordinating the metal in the two species. More recently, we showed that the fully active state of the enzyme is attained only after redox activation by reduction of a surface-exposed disulfide bridge (Cys845-Cys872)³⁵ and that the intensity of the W^V signal is closely related to the amount of active state, where both species are also observed. The EPR analysis of anaerobically isolated U192C revealed the presence of W^V_F as the major species, with a smaller amount of W^V_D , indicating that the enzyme is mostly isolated in a partly reduced form (Figure 3a). Depending on the preparation, the initial amount of the U192C W^V signal represents 20–25% in spin intensity. The presence of both W^V signals reveals that the two W^V_F and W^V_D species can be present even in the absence of an added reductant and thus correspond to close conformations of the W-cofactor that can be spontaneously stabilized. To promote complete reduction of the U192C variant, an excess of either formate or dithionite was added, with formate clearly favoring the W^V_F signal (Figure 3b), while dithionite led to the concomitant presence of both types of W^V signals in nearly

Figure 3. EPR spectra of W^V -U192C and comparison with WT. (a) Experimental spectrum of U192C (37 μ M) as-isolated anaerobically ($E = -372$ mV) (x20, for clarity); (b) U192C (96 μ M) reduced with formate (10 scans) and its simulation in red (b-sim); (c) U192C (96 μ M) reduced with dithionite (10 scans); (d), spectral difference between (b) and (c), its simulation in red (d-sim); (e) WT (50 μ M) poised at -395 mV by formate (x20 for clarity) and its simulation (e-sim). Simulation parameters in Table 2. Experimental conditions: temperature 80 K, microwave power 40 mW, modulation amplitude 1 mT at 100 kHz, and microwave frequency 9.481 GHz.

equal proportions (Figure 3c). These relative proportions result from variations in the equilibrium between the distinct forms of the W-bis-MGD cofactor influenced by the nature of the reductant used, as previously observed.³⁷ Taking the difference between both spectra, it is possible to obtain the pure signature of the W^V_D signal in U192C (Figure 3d).

Interestingly, the W^V signals of the U192C variant reveal only weak changes due to the replacement of Se with S, but careful analysis of the g -values (Table 2) shows that this amino acid substitution results in a small change in the W^V g -tensor anisotropy, with a slight decrease of g anisotropy for both W^V species when going from WT to U192C. This decrease in g -tensor anisotropy, together with the decrease in g_1 when changing Sec to Cys, agrees with the decrease in the covalency of the metal–ligand bond expected for the replacement of the Se ligand by S.^{39–41} Moreover, it is interesting to note that the value of the hyperfine coupling parameter A_{iso} of ¹⁸³W is not affected by Se/S substitution, as observed in model W complexes.⁴¹ The weakness of these variations is likely due to the high number of sulfur atoms in the coordination sphere of the W^V ion, leading to only a small perturbation upon replacement of one of the sulfurs by a selenium atom. Moreover, no difference was observed for the [FeS] cluster EPR signals between U192C and WT (Figure S2) showing that the Sec-to-Cys replacement has no effect on the structural properties or relative arrangement of these centers.

To confirm that Sec is bound to the W ion in the EPR-detected W^V species, ⁷⁷Se-labeled FdhAB was produced to analyze hyperfine couplings of ⁷⁷Se ($I = 1/2$) to W^V ion. DTT-activated ⁷⁷Se-FdhAB was reduced with either formate or dithionite. The W^V signal could be identified in both preparations, and both W^V_F and W^V_D signals revealed clear splittings due to the presence of ⁷⁷Se (Figure 4). In both cases,

Table 2. EPR Parameters Used for Simulation of the W^V species Signals^a

	g_1	g_2	g_3	g -anisotropy	g -rhombicity
U192C: S- W^V_F	1.986 (0.0075)	1.880 (0.006)	1.855 (0.006)	0.131	0.81
U192C: S- W^V_D	1.989 (0.0080)	1.913 (0.0055)	1.854 (0.0060)	0.135	0.56
WT: Se- W^V_F	1.993 (0.0075)	1.881 (0.006)	1.852 (0.006)	0.141	0.79
⁷⁷ Se- W^V_D	1.993 (0.0075)	1.911 (0.006)	1.853 (0.007)	0.140	0.58
⁷⁷ Se- W^V_F	1.993 (0.008)	1.882 (0.006)	1.852 (0.007)	0.141	0.78
Hyperfine parameters ¹⁸³ W (MHz)	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_{iso}	
U192C: S- W^V_F	210	131	140	160	
U192C: S- W^V_D	227	112	132	157	
WT: Se- W^V_F	224	129	134	162	
Hyperfine parameters ⁷⁷ Se (MHz)	A_1	A_2	A_3		
(80%) ⁷⁷ Se- W^V_D	224	280	224	243	
(80%) ⁷⁷ Se- W^V_F	196	132	168	165	

^aAnisotropy (g_1-g_3) and rhombicity ($(g_1-g_2)/(g_1-g_3)$) were also calculated. Spectral broadening was described by the g -strain effect (parameters in brackets). The natural abundance of ¹⁸³W ($I = 1/2$, 14.3%) was also considered, except in signals given by ⁷⁷Se enriched FdhAB. Hyperfine coupling constants are given in MHz. Uncertainties on g -values are typically 0.001, and 5 MHz on hyperfine coupling constants. A_{iso} is calculated from $A_{iso} = (A_1 + A_2 + A_3)/3$.

Figure 4. EPR spectra of reduced ⁷⁷Se-FdhAB. A Experimental spectrum of DTT-treated ⁷⁷Se-FdhAB reduced with formate (black line). B Experimental spectrum of DTT-treated ⁷⁷Se-FdhAB reduced with dithionite (black line). The spectral simulations (parameters given in Table 2) are colored red considering 80% ⁷⁷Se. The dotted red line corresponds to the signal simulation considering 100% ⁷⁷Se, with the parameters given in Table 2. EPR experimental conditions as in Figure 3.

the presence of a small amount of the remaining unsplit signal (~20%) is consistent with the presence of 80% ⁷⁷Se, as expected from the enrichment protocol. The hyperfine splittings that result from the ⁷⁷Se-W coordination are well resolved on X-band EPR spectra, and simulations enable to determine hyperfine coupling parameters with good accuracy (Table 2). Interestingly, the ⁷⁷Se hyperfine coupling is much more isotropic and intense in W^V_F and W^V_D species than that estimated in Mo/Sec EcFDH-H enriched with ⁷⁷Se.⁴² The ⁷⁷Se A_{iso} values calculated from our experimental data for W^V_F (165 MHz) and W^V_D (243 MHz) are significantly higher than those obtained in EcFDH-H (~100 MHz),⁴² but they are similar to those found in NiFeSe hydrogenase, in which the Sec is directly bound to the metal ion, for instance, in the Ni-

CO(⁷⁷Se) state (185 MHz).⁴³ These ⁷⁷Se A_{iso} values enabled the estimation of the spin density carried by the Se atom at about 15 to 22% in W^V_F and W^V_D species, respectively. Such a high value of spin density clearly shows that Sec remains bound to W^V ion in the two observed W^V species.

Crystal Structure of the U192C Variant. The U192C variant could be crystallized under anaerobic conditions, and well-diffracting crystals were obtained for as-isolated U192C (PDB ID: 9QM0) as well as for U192C treated with dithionite for 1 min (U192C_dithio, PDB ID: 9QM1). The fully refined crystal structures revealed that the U192C mutation does not change the overall structure of the enzyme, and both structures (U192C and U192C_dithio) are structurally very similar (RMSD of 0.28 Å for 1182 Cα). Moreover, the U192C

Figure 5. Comparison of the structure of the U192C variant with that of C872A (activated state) and the oxidized WT FdhAB (resting state). Superposition of U192C structure (green, PDB ID: 9QM0) with C872A (blue, PDB ID: 8CM6),³⁵ in panels (a) and (c), and with FdhAB WT (gray)(PDB ID: 6SDR),²³ in (b) and (d). The sulfur, selenium, and tungsten atoms are shown in yellow, orange, and gray blue, respectively. Distances are given in Å.

mutation was confirmed by the electron density at the W site, with corresponding B-factors in the same range (18–27 Å²). Interestingly, the U192C variant presents a conformation that corresponds to the active state of the enzyme, as it is fully superimposable with that of the C872A variant (PDB ID: 8CM6, Figure 5a,c RMSD of 0.44 Å, for 1181 Cα).³⁵ The C872A variant was designed to mimic the activated form of FdhAB (with the surface C845–C872 disulfide bond reduced).³⁵ The opening of this disulfide bond leads to allosteric conformational changes that are transduced to the active site and result in a drastic reduction in the K_M for formate and an increase in formate dehydrogenase activity, but decrease the enzyme's resistance to oxygen inactivation.³⁵ In the U192C structure, the C845–C872 disulfide bond is reduced, and the same allosteric conformational changes present in C872A are observed, spanning about 25 Å from the disulfide bond to the buried active site (Figure 5). As previously described,³⁵ these major conformational changes involve residues L843, P842, H410, W407, Q409, and M405, leading to changes in the geometry of the active site. Residues M405 and Q409 are the major ones responsible for this change in geometry (Figure 5d), as M405 causes the reorientation of U192, while Q409 moves closer to the MGD2 cofactor and creates a new H-bond with N5 (IUPAC numbering; N15 in the PDB) from the pterin. We also observe a reorientation of the catalytic residues H193 and R441 (Figure 6).³⁵ This activated protein form was obtained for the U192C variant without addition of DTT because the enzyme was purified, crystallized, and handled under anaerobic conditions, and the native active state was thus preserved. In contrast, oxidizing the cell lysate before enzyme purification leads to the formation of

the disulfide bond, generating the resting, protected state of FdhAB.³⁵

Remarkably, the catalytic residue R441 was found in a double conformation for both U192C and U192C_dithio, in which R441a (50% occupancy) is in the orientation usually observed for the WT and C872A variants, while R441b (50% occupancy) corresponds to a new rotamer that places the guanidinium moiety closer to the metal site (Figure 6a,c). In both structures, two water molecules could be modeled near the active site (Figure 6a–c). These water molecules are not present in WT structures, although in the C872A variant, one water molecule is found at position 1 (Figure 6d,e). In addition, R441b in U192C_dithio is slightly shifted when compared with U192C (Figure 6b,c), and its guanidinium moiety is interacting with a modeled SO₂ molecule located 3.0 Å from C192 S_γ. The SO₂ molecule was refined with an occupancy of 31%, whereas the two water molecules were refined with an occupancy of 69%. The presence of the ligand and water molecules in the U192C_dithio structure is validated by the omitted map presented in Figure 6c. The modeled SO₂ molecule is stabilized by two hydrogen bonds with the R441b side chain (the SO₂ oxygen atoms are interacting with the Nε and Nη1 atoms, respectively), plus an interaction with the C192–S_γ (Figure 6c). The absence of the SO₂ ligand in the U192C structure is validated by the electron density map and by the different conformation of R441b, which is no longer in a position that would allow two hydrogen bonds to form if a similar molecule were located at the SO₂ site (Figure 6a,b).

Figure 6. Details of the U192C active site and comparison with C872A and WT-FdhAB. (a) U192C structure (green, PDB ID: 9QM0) with two water molecules near the W site and R441 also in double conformation (each conformer with 50% occupancy). The 2Fo-Fc electron density map, contoured at 1σ , is shown as a blue mesh. (b) Superposition of the U192C_dithio structure (violet, PDB ID: 9QM1) and U192C structure (green, PDB ID: 9QM0). (c) U192C_dithio structure (violet, PDB ID: 9QM1) showing an SO₂ (31% occupancy) and two water molecules (69% occupancy) at the active site and the double conformation of R441 (each conformer with 50% occupancy). The sulfur, selenium, and tungsten atoms are shown in yellow, orange, and gray blue, respectively. The 2Fo-Fc electron density map, contoured at 1σ , is shown as a blue mesh. Hydrogen bonds and interactions between the SO₂ molecule and FdhAB_U192C are shown as orange and black dashes, respectively. Distances are indicated in Å. In the inset, the omit difference map for the SO₂ plus two H₂O molecules with different occupancies is represented, contoured at 4σ (green mesh). (d) Superposition of U192C_dithio structure (violet, PDB ID: 9QM1) and C872A (blue, PDB ID: 8CM6).³⁵ (e) Superposition of U192C_dithio structure (violet, PDB ID: 9QM1) and WT-FdhAB (pink, PDB ID: 6SDR).²³

DISCUSSION

The role of Sec in improving the activity of redox enzymes has been demonstrated for several selenoproteins, including glycine reductase, methionine sulfoxide reductase, glutathione peroxidase, and hydrogenase.^{15,44–46} In several FDHs, a Cys replaces the Sec and is usually bound to Mo, but these enzymes typically display lower catalytic efficiencies.^{47,48} Our results show that in *N. vulgaris* H W/Sec-FdhAB, the Se-to-S substitution strongly reduces the rate and overall efficiency of both formate oxidation and CO₂ reduction. The decrease in K_M for formate observed for the U192C variant also contributes strongly to its large efficiency decrease. Notably, the effect of this substitution in this W-dependent enzyme (4% formate oxidation activity, 9% CO₂ reduction activity) is stronger than that recently reported with the Sec-to-Cys variant of the Mo/Sec-EcFDH-H (48% formate oxidation activity and 19% CO₂ reduction activity),²⁵ suggesting a possible stronger effect of Sec in the W-dependent enzyme, although the effect of the protein environment (not analyzed in that study) will also play a role. Interestingly, the U192C variant still displays a higher CO₂ reduction activity than that reported for most Mo enzymes, confirming the important role played by W in this activity. The high activity of the W/Sec-FdhAB is reflected in a strong physiological preference for this enzyme in *N. vulgaris* H, since it is strongly upregulated in the presence of W, whereas a Mo-FDH is repressed.⁴⁹ The W facilitates low-potential redox reactions, such as CO₂ reduction.^{27,50}

The small kinetic isotope effects observed with D-formate are in line with previous studies of FDHs^{28,48,51,52} (Table S1), and suggest that breakage of the formate C–H bond is not the rate-limiting step. Nevertheless, the greater kinetic effect observed for the U192C variant relative to the WT may suggest the involvement of this residue in the proton-transfer pathway, as observed for the [NiFeSe] hydrogenase.¹⁵ In the [NiFe] hydrogenases, it has been clearly proven that the terminal Cys ligand to the Ni, corresponding to Sec in [NiFeSe] hydrogenases, is involved in H⁺ transfer to and from the active site.^{53,54} This Cys was recently replaced with a Sec in the bidirectional *E. coli* hydrogenase-2, causing the H₂ production activity to be greatly enhanced relative to the H₂ oxidation one.⁴⁶ This is in line with the higher H₂ production activities of [NiFeSe] hydrogenases and suggests that Sec is more efficient than Cys in promoting H⁺ transfer to the active site.⁴⁶ If a parallel is drawn for FDHs, then the presence of Sec in these enzymes may promote H⁺ transfer for CO₂ reduction, in line with observed results. Se has a lower pK_a than S (5.2 for SeH vs 8.3 for SH) and thus a lower proton affinity at physiological pH. In terms of the enzyme's optimum pH, our results reveal that the U192C variant has a lower pH optimum for formate oxidation, whereas there is only a minor effect for CO₂ reduction. A lower pH optimum may seem contradictory to the expected variation in pK_as, suggesting an important role of the protein environment, but agrees with the higher stability at acidic pHs observed for the Cys variant of the Sec/Mo EcFDH-H.²⁵

Our results agree with previous findings in that the pressure to retain the more costly Sec over Cys is related not only to increased enzymatic activity but also to a higher tolerance to O₂. Although Se is more easily oxidized than S,^{1,4,9} the latter can reach oxidation states that are not possible to revert.⁷ Our chronoamperometry studies evaluating the enzyme activity in

the presence of O₂ confirm that WT Sec-FdhAB is globally more resistant to O₂, even though its O₂-bound state inactivates more quickly than the O₂-bound state of U192C. On the other hand, the affinity for O₂ is much lower for the Sec-containing WT enzyme than for U192C. Overall, the incorporation of Sec results in an enzyme that is 8 times more resistant to O₂ than the Cys-equivalent enzyme. This is a great advantage for enzymes present in anaerobic bacteria, which may be transiently exposed to small levels of O₂, and may therefore be a major contribution to the evolutionary pressure of retaining Sec. In the *N. vulgaris* H W/Sec-FdhAB, this short-term protection mechanism is complemented by the disulfide allosteric switch mechanism that acts in long-term protection.³⁵

The small effect of the Sec-to-Cys substitution in the W^V EPR spectra suggests that the constraints imposed by the pterin cofactor and surrounding amino acids, namely the second coordination sphere of the metal, play a more important role in controlling the electronic structure of the active site than the Sec coordination.⁵⁵ More importantly, the hyperfine splittings observed for W^V EPR signals in the presence of ⁷⁷Se lead to hyperfine coupling constants between the ⁷⁷Se nucleus and the metal ion that are larger or similar to those measured in other ⁷⁷Se-enriched metalloenzymes,^{42,43} where Sec is coordinating the metal center. This constitutes clear evidence that the Sec remains bound to the W ion in the FdhAB W^V redox state. The increased covalency created by the inclusion of Sec in a coordination already rich in S at a Mo/W active site³⁹ can alter the metal redox potential, facilitating the hydride transfer from formate to the sulfido group. Although the reaction mechanism of FDHs is still under discussion, there is increasing evidence of the direct hydride transfer mechanism.^{37,48,56,57} A recent computational study of the enzymatic mechanism for CO₂ reduction³⁶ pointed to the importance of a stable hexa-coordination of the Mo/W atom for enzyme specificity, since an open coordination site would enable the formation of a metal-hydride and consequently the production of H₂, which is not observed in FDHs.

Notably, the observation of the previously characterized activated conformation,³⁵ with a reduced C845–C872 disulfide bond, in the variant U192C, which is fully capable of establishing this bond (unlike the C872A variant), confirms the proposed redox switch mechanism involving this disulfide.³⁵ The present structure of the U192C variant was obtained from enzyme purified, crystallized, and always handled under anaerobic conditions, which prevented the formation of the C845–C872 disulfide bond, keeping the two thiol groups in the reduced form. In contrast, earlier structures were obtained with enzyme isolated and crystallized under aerobic conditions, which led to the formation of this bond. The modeled SO₂ molecule present in the U192C_dithio structure was likely generated by the crystal soaking with dithionite, as SO₂ is a well-known byproduct of dithionite degradation.⁵⁸ Some SO₂ was captured by FdhAB, resulting in a partially occupied site close to the W active site, with the remaining protein molecules containing two water molecules, as observed in the as-isolated U192C structure. Interestingly, the second conformation of the R441 side chain stabilizing the SO₂ molecule has never been observed before. We hypothesize that the U192C mutation led to changes in the dynamics of the local environment near the active site, allowing for the stabilization of a new conformation of the R441 catalytic residue. This arginine has been proposed in several studies to

be crucial for catalytic activity, by playing a role in the stabilization and proper orientation of the substrate toward the active site.^{33,36} The position and conformation of R441b are identical to the catalytic intermediate proposed through computational studies (after addition of one proton and two electrons).³⁶ The presence of the substrate analog SO₂ led to the stabilization of the second conformation of R441, as seen in the U192C_dithio structure. As the Mo-containing enzyme used in that computational study (formate dehydrogenase N from *Escherichia coli* (PDB ID: 1KQF)) is structurally very similar to the active conformation of FdhAB, comparisons can be drawn. In fact, the distance between the ligand and one of the R441 N η 2 hydrogens is 1.9 Å in the U192C_dithio structure and 1.8 Å in the computational model (Figure 6c). The distances between the ligand and the amide nitrogen of G442 (U192C_dithio), or of H448 in the computational model, are 2.4 Å and 2.1 Å, respectively.³⁶ It is therefore likely that the U192C_dithio crystal structure corresponds to the first structurally characterized proxy of a catalytic intermediate of FdhAB, confirming the critical role of R441 in positioning the substrates in the correct orientation for catalysis and offering valuable insights into the catalytic mechanism of FDHs. Nevertheless, further experiments are necessary to better detail the mechanistic steps and intermediates involved, namely time-resolved crystallography studies that are currently being pursued.

CONCLUSION

In summary, we show that Sec coordination to W is maintained in the W^V intermediate and that Sec is not only responsible for an increased activity of FdhAB but also for an increased catalytic efficiency. Structural studies captured the U192C variant in the activated state and showed the catalytically essential Arg in a second conformation stabilizing an SO₂ molecule, which is a CO₂ analog. This is the first structural evidence of a possible catalytic intermediate in CO₂ reduction, confirming the computational predictions. Overall, the results agree with a stable Sec coordination to W during the catalytic cycle and a likely involvement of Sec in the proton transfer pathway, as observed for the [NiFe] and [NiFeSe] hydrogenases. Finally, Sec also offers a marked advantage in increasing the tolerance to O₂ and preventing irreversible inactivation. This is an important feature for enzymes found in anaerobic bacteria that may be transiently exposed to small amounts of O₂. This effect is a major contributor to the evolutionary pressure of retaining Sec and is also a major advantage for the use of FdhAB in biotechnological applications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Site-Directed Mutagenesis, Expression, and Protein Purification. The U192C variant of *N. vulgaris* H FdhAB was produced by site-directed mutagenesis of the *fdhA* gene in the pRec-FdhAB-Strep expression plasmid²³ using the NZYMutagenesis kit. The mutagenic primers used are presented in Table S2. Correct mutations were confirmed through sequencing by Eurofins Genomics, Germany. Electroporation was performed as previously described in the *N. vulgaris* H Δ *fdhAB* deletion strain.^{23,59,60} Cells were grown as previously described.^{23,35}

For the ⁷⁷Se-labeled FdhAB, 160 mg of 99% elemental [⁷⁷Se]-selenium (Sigma-Aldrich) was acidified by the addition of 500 μ L of 65% nitric acid. This was allowed to dissolve for 1

h before diluting with H₂O to obtain [⁷⁷Se]-selenite, which was then supplemented in the growth medium to a final concentration of 3 μ M. The growth inoculum was a source of at least 1 μ M of additional Se, resulting in \sim 75% ⁷⁷Se.

Unless otherwise stated, FdhAB was aerobically purified, while U192C was typically anaerobically purified. Purification protocols were performed as described in refs ^{23,35}. The buffer of pure samples was exchanged to 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 10% (v/v) glycerol, and 10 mM NaNO₃ (Buffer A). Protein concentration was routinely determined based on $\epsilon_{410\text{nm}} = 43.45 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ ref ²³. Purity of the samples was judged by 12% SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis.

Solution Activity Assays. Routine solution enzymatic assays were performed as previously described,²³ with or without 5 min of preincubation with 50 mM DTT for the WT and the U192C variant, respectively, using a UV-1800 Shimadzu spectrophotometer inside a COY anaerobic chamber with an atmosphere of 2% H₂/98% N₂. Benzyl viologen (2 mM) was used as an electron acceptor for formate oxidation and zinc-reduced methyl viologen (0.1 mM) as an electron donor for CO₂ reduction. A final concentration of 1.4 nM of enzyme was used for both WT FdhAB and the U192C variant. The activity of the WT enzyme was confirmed to be similar to the reported value.²³

The influence of pH on U192C activity was evaluated using a mix of glycine, K₂HPO₄, citric acid, and Tris buffers (25 mM each). The pH was adjusted using HCl or KOH.

For determination of the K_M constants, the activity of the pure enzyme was measured at sodium formate and sodium D-formate concentrations ranging from 0.5 μ M to 20 mM (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Inc.) in 50 mM KP_i buffer at pH of 7.6. In the case of CO₂ 75 μ M to 50 mM of sodium bicarbonate were used in 50 mM KP_i buffer at a pH 7.1.

Electrochemical Methods. All measurements were performed inside a Jacomex glovebox with an atmosphere of N₂ (O₂ < 4 ppm). The electrochemical evaluations were performed in a standard three-electrode cell, with a platinum wire as the counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl electrode as the reference electrode. Electroactive protein films were prepared by coadsorption of the enzyme with polymyxin B sulfate (Sigma-Aldrich) on a pyrolytic graphite edge rotating disc electrode (PGE-RDE, 2.5 mm diameter). For this, 0.5 μ L of 6 mg/mL polymyxin was deposited in PGE-RDE and allowed to dry; then, 0.5 μ L of 7.4 μ M enzyme solution was added, and the electrode was used immediately before drying, as described in ref ⁶¹. In the case of WT FdhAB, 1 μ L of 74 μ M enzyme was preincubated with 1 μ L of 10 mM DTT for 10 min before being diluted to 7.4 μ M using buffer E (100 mM NaCl, 5 mM MES, 5 mM CHES, 5 mM HEPES, 5 mM TAPS, 5 mM sodium acetate, and pH 7.0). The anaerobically purified U192C variant was directly diluted to the same final concentration. An Autolab PGSTAT128N potentiostat (Metrohm, The Netherlands) was used with the GPES software. An Autolab RDE 2 electrode rotator (Metrohm, The Netherlands) was used to control the working electrode rotation to around 4000 rpm. Chronoamperometric measurements were performed with the potential poised at $E = +130 \text{ mV}$ vs standard hydrogen electrode (SHE). Additions of 30 μ M O₂ were performed by injecting 50 μ L of O₂-saturated H₂O in the cell containing 1 mM formate in buffer E. The data were analyzed using the open-source program QSoas,⁶² available at qsoas.org. For statistical analysis, GraphPad Prism Software (San Diego, CA, USA) was used, applying

Welch's unequal variances *t*-test. Differences were considered significant when *p*-value was $*p < 0.05$.

EPR Spectroscopy and Samples Preparation. All the samples were prepared inside a Jacomex glovebox at room temperature, in buffer M (50 mM MOPS, pH 7.6, 10% (v/v) glycerol). Redox potentials were measured with a combined Pt-Ag/AgCl/KCl (3 M) microelectrode. A cocktail of redox mediators (10 μ M each), consisting of methylene blue (11 mV), indigo disulfonate (−125 mV), phenosafranine (−252 mV), methyl red (−325 mV), and methyl viologen (−440 mV), was added to U192C (37 μ M). After equilibration, small additions of sodium formate (20–100 mM in an O₂-free MOPS buffer) were used to reduce the sample. In a second analysis, U192C (96 μ M) was directly reduced by adding excess dithionite or formate.

For formate reduction, ⁷⁷Se-FdhAB (96 μ M) was reduced with 50 mM DTT and 20 mM formate for 20 min directly in the EPR tube in the presence of the redox mediator mix. On the other hand, for dithionite reduction, ⁷⁷Se-FdhAB was activated with DTT for 5–10 min, the excess DTT was washed off with buffer M using a 30 kDa cutoff ultracentrifugation unit, and then reduction with excess dithionite was performed.

Samples were transferred to EPR tubes and frozen immediately inside the glovebox using an ethanol bath refrigerated with liquid nitrogen from the outside. All potentials are quoted against the SHE. Frozen samples were transferred out of the glovebox and kept in liquid nitrogen.

EPR measurements were performed on a Bruker ELEXSYS E500 spectrometer equipped with an ER4102ST standard rectangular Bruker EPR cavity, fitted to an Oxford Instruments ESR 900 helium flow cryostat. Spin intensity measurements were performed by double integration of EPR spectra recorded in nonsaturating conditions and compared to a 1 mM Cu^{II}-EDTA standard. EPR spectrum simulations were performed with EasySpin software.

X-ray Crystallography and Structure Refinement. The crystal structures reported in this work were obtained from protein samples purified in anaerobiosis (see above), with all crystals produced in the anaerobic chamber under an argon atmosphere (<0.1 ppm of oxygen). The hanging-drop vapor diffusion method, at 20 °C in 24-well plates (24-well XRL plate, Molecular Dimensions), was used to obtain FdhAB U192C single crystals from drops of 2 μ L (1:1, protein:precipitant ratio). U192C (in 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 10% (v/v) glycerol, 10 mM NaNO₃ buffer) was crystallized using solutions with 26–34% PEG 3350 (w/v), 0.1 M Tris-HCl pH 8.0, and 1 M LiCl as precipitant,²³ supplemented with 0.2 μ L of a 1:500 dilution from a stock of FdhAB wild-type microseeds.⁶³ Crystals of U192C FdhAB appeared within 24 h, and after 72 h, crystals were flash-cooled in liquid nitrogen and cryoprotected in a 20% (v/v) glycerol-supplemented precipitant solution. Additionally, to obtain the U192C_dithio structure, a 1-min soaking with 10 mM sodium dithionite was performed prior to flash cooling. All of the solutions used were previously degassed and stored in the anaerobic chamber.

X-ray diffraction experiments were conducted, at 100 K on beamline ID30A-3⁶⁴ at the ESRF synchrotron (Grenoble, France). Data processing was performed with XDS⁶⁵ and Aimless⁶⁶ software. Molecular replacement with Phaser⁶⁷ from the CCP4 suite⁶⁸ was used to solve the structures, using the as-isolated WT FdhAB structure (PDB ID: 6SDR) as a search model. The molecular models were refined with iterative cycles of manual model building with Coot⁶⁹ and REFMACS

automatic restrained refinement.⁷⁰ The online PDBredo server⁷¹ was used to perform model rebuilding, and publication images were generated on PyMOL⁷² Data processing and model refinement statistics are given in Table S3.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acscatal.5c02382>.

Enzyme kinetics; iron–sulfur center EPR spectra; comparison of kinetic isotope effects of different FDHs; list of primers used for mutagenesis; and crystallographic diffraction and refinement data (PDF)

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Author Contributions

I.A.C.P. and A.R.O. conceived the project and were involved in bacterial growth, protein production and purification, bio-

chemical characterization, and enzymatic assays. A.R.O., C.L., and V.F. were involved in the electrochemical studies. A.R.O., F.B., and B.G. were involved in the EPR studies. G.V.-A., C.M., and M.J.R. were involved in the crystallographic studies. I.A.C.P. and A.R.O. wrote the manuscript with input from all authors, who approved the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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ABBREVIATIONS

FDH, Formate dehydrogenase; GPX4, glutathione peroxidase 4; *N. vulgaris* H, *Nitratidessulfovibrio vulgaris* Hildenborough; MGD, molybdopterin guanine dinucleotides; PGE-RDE, pyrolytic graphite edge rotating disk electrode; SEH, standard hydrogen electrode

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